

QUANTUM-RESILIENT ADAPTIVE NETWORK SECURITY MODEL FOR IOT AND EDGE COMPUTING INFRASTRUCTURES

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Abstract. This article proposes a quantum-resilient adaptive network security model for IoT and edge computing infrastructures. The model integrates firewalls, IDPS, Zero Trust, post-quantum cryptography, and resource-aware optimization. BIKE is used for secure key exchange, NTRUEncrypt for data encryption, and SPHINCS+ for digital signatures and integrity protection. The proposed approach improves security, performance, and quantum resilience in modern IoT and edge environments.

Keywords. post-quantum cryptography, network security, IoT, edge computing, firewall, IDPS, Zero Trust, NTRUEncrypt, SPHINCS+, BIKE

INTRODUCTION

Modern digital infrastructures increasingly depend on IoT devices, edge computing nodes, 5G communication systems, cloud platforms, and distributed services. These technologies improve automation, real-time data processing, and service availability, but they also expand the cyberattack surface. Recent studies separately address post-quantum cryptographic algorithms for secure data transmission [1], advanced multi-layered network security strategies [2], and optimization of hybrid post-quantum cryptographic frameworks in resource-constrained environments [3].

The security problem becomes more complex when current network threats and future quantum threats are considered together. Traditional network attacks include malware, ransomware, phishing, unauthorized access, botnets, insider threats, distributed denial-of-service attacks, and Man-in-the-Middle attacks. At the same time, quantum computing threatens classical public-key cryptographic systems. Shor's algorithm can solve integer factorization and discrete logarithm problems efficiently on a quantum computer, making RSA and ECC vulnerable in the future [4]. Grover's algorithm also reduces the complexity of exhaustive search, which affects symmetric security assumptions [5].

Post-quantum cryptography provides a promising direction for protecting data against future quantum adversaries. However, post-quantum algorithms may require more memory, larger keys, and higher computational resources than classical algorithms. This

creates a challenge for IoT and edge environments, where devices often have limited processing power, memory, and energy capacity.

The purpose of this article is to develop an integrated security model that combines classical network defense and post-quantum cryptography. The proposed model includes Zero Trust verification, firewall filtering, IDPS-based threat detection, network segmentation, BIKE-based key exchange, NTRUEncrypt-based encryption, SPHINCS+-based digital signature, and resource-aware optimization for ARM and FPGA platforms.

The scientific novelty of the article is the development of a unified quantum-resilient adaptive network security model that can protect IoT and edge infrastructures from both conventional cyberattacks and future quantum-enabled cryptographic attacks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Post-quantum cryptography is an important research area aimed at designing algorithms resistant to both classical and quantum attacks. Bernstein, Buchmann, and Dahmen describe several post-quantum cryptographic families, including lattice-based, hash-based, code-based, and multivariate approaches [6]. These approaches rely on mathematical problems that are believed to remain difficult even for quantum computers.

Lattice-based cryptography is widely studied because of its strong security and practical efficiency. NTRUEncrypt is a well-known lattice-based public-key cryptosystem that can be used for efficient encryption and

supports implementation optimization [7]. In hybrid post-quantum frameworks, NTRUEncrypt is often selected for protecting data confidentiality due to its balance between security and speed.

Hash-based cryptography is mainly used for digital signatures. SPHINCS+ is a stateless hash-based signature scheme designed for post-quantum security [8]. It provides authenticity, integrity, and non-repudiation, which are essential in IoT and edge systems where sensor data and control commands must be protected against modification.

Code-based cryptography relies on the difficulty of decoding random linear codes. BIKE is a code-based key encapsulation mechanism that can be used for secure session key establishment [9]. Its low-latency key exchange capability makes it suitable for real-time communication systems and edge infrastructures.

Network security studies emphasize that cryptographic protection alone is not enough. Firewalls, intrusion detection systems, access control, encryption, and continuous monitoring must be integrated into a multi-layered architecture. Zero Trust Architecture strengthens this approach by requiring continuous verification of users, devices, and access requests instead of automatically trusting internal network traffic [10].

Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems are essential for identifying suspicious behavior and preventing attacks. Machine learning methods can improve intrusion detection by identifying anomalies and reducing false positives [11]. This is especially important in IoT and 5G networks, where large numbers of devices generate continuous traffic.

Code-based cryptography has a long historical foundation. The McEliece cryptosystem, introduced in 1978, remains one of the oldest post-quantum public-key cryptosystems and has resisted many cryptanalytic attacks [12]. Its security background supports the relevance of code-based methods such as BIKE in hybrid post-quantum systems.

Table 1. Research areas integrated in the proposed model

Research area	Main components	Security function
Network security	Firewall, IDPS, Zero Trust	Protection against current cyber threats

Post-quantum cryptography	NTRUEncrypt, SPHINCS+, BIKE	Protection against future quantum attacks
Resource-aware optimization	ARM, FPGA, energy control	Efficient deployment in IoT and edge environments
Adaptive response	Risk scoring, isolation, re-keying	Dynamic incident mitigation

The literature review shows that modern cybersecurity requires a combined architecture. A secure IoT or edge system must detect network attacks, verify users and devices, protect transmitted data, resist future quantum attacks, and operate efficiently under resource constraints.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study is based on structural modeling and comparative analysis. The proposed model combines three security directions: multi-layered network defense, hybrid post-quantum cryptography, and resource-aware optimization.

The proposed architecture consists of seven main layers.

1. Zero Trust access layer.

This layer verifies each user, device, and application before granting access. It uses multi-factor authentication, device identity, role-based access control, and contextual risk evaluation. The principle of this layer is that no device or user is trusted by default.

2. Firewall and segmentation layer.

This layer filters network traffic and divides the infrastructure into separate zones. For example, IoT devices, edge gateways, cloud servers, administrative systems, and user devices are placed into different segments. This reduces the risk of lateral movement during an attack.

3. IDPS and AI-based monitoring layer.

This layer monitors traffic and detects suspicious behavior. It combines signature-based detection, anomaly-based detection, and machine learning-supported monitoring. If suspicious activity is detected, the system forwards the event to the risk analysis module.

4. post-quantum key exchange layer.

This layer uses BIKE to establish secure session keys between communicating devices. The purpose of

this layer is to protect session establishment from quantum-enabled attacks.

5. post-quantum encryption layer.

This layer uses NTRUEncrypt to encrypt transmitted data. It provides quantum-resistant confidentiality for IoT, edge, and cloud communication.

6. Digital signature layer.

This layer uses SPHINCS+ to sign messages and verify their integrity. It ensures that transmitted data has not been modified and that the sender is authentic.

7. Resource-aware optimization layer.

This layer selects the execution mode according to device capability. ARM-based IoT nodes use lightweight processing, while FPGA-based edge gateways use accelerated processing for high-throughput and energy-efficient cryptographic operations.

Experimental environment and software tools

For practical validation, the proposed model can be evaluated in a mixed IoT and edge computing test environment. The IoT side may be represented by Raspberry Pi 4 Model B or ARM Cortex-A53 class embedded devices, while the edge acceleration side may be represented by an FPGA-based platform such as Xilinx Kintex-7. This configuration makes it possible to compare lightweight software execution with hardware-accelerated cryptographic processing.

The software environment may include Ubuntu Core or Ubuntu 22.04 LTS, Python 3.10, GCC/C++ compiler tools, Open Quantum Safe libraries such as liboqs and PyOQS for post-quantum key exchange and encryption experiments, and reference implementations of SPHINCS+ and BIKE. Network traffic and attack scenarios can be simulated using Mininet, Wireshark, Snort or Suricata IDS, and IoT traffic generators. This setup provides a realistic basis for evaluating firewall filtering, IDPS detection, post-quantum encryption, signature verification, key exchange latency, memory usage, and energy consumption in IoT and edge environments.

Table 2. Recommended experimental environment for model validation

Component	Recommended tool or platform	Purpose
IoT device	Raspberry Pi 4 / ARM Cortex-A53	Resource-constrained execution

Edge accelerator	Xilinx Kintex-7 FPGA	Hardware acceleration
Operating system	Ubuntu Core / Ubuntu 22.04 LTS	Test environment
PQC library	liboqs / PyOQS	BIKE and NTRUEncrypt testing
Signature implementation	SPHINCS+ reference code	Digital signature testing
IDPS tool	Snort / Suricata	DDoS and MitM detection
Traffic analysis	Wireshark / Mininet	Network monitoring and simulation

Mathematical model

The total secure transmission time of the proposed model is calculated as follows:

$$T_{secure} = T_{zt} + T_{f\omega} + T_{idps} + T_{kex} + T_{enc} + T_{sig} + T_{ver} + T_{comm}$$

where:

T_{secure} - is the total secure transmission time;

T_{zt} - is the Zero Trust verification time;

$T_{f\omega}$ - is the firewall filtering time;

T_{idps} - is the IDPS processing time;

T_{kex} - is the BIKE-based key exchange time;

T_{enc} - is the NTRUEncrypt encryption time;

T_{sig} - is the SPHINCS+ signature generation

time;

T_{ver} - is the signature verification time;

T_{comm} - is the communication delay.

The adaptive security efficiency coefficient is defined as:

$$E = \frac{S \times Q}{T_{secure} \times P \times M}$$

where:

E - is the adaptive security efficiency coefficient;

C - is the general security level;

Q - is the quantum-resistance factor;

P - is the energy consumption;

M - is the memory consumption.

A higher value of E means that the selected configuration provides strong security and quantum resistance with lower delay, energy consumption, and memory overhead.

The risk score for network events is calculated as:

$$R = \alpha A + \beta V + \gamma D + \lambda C$$

where:

R - is the total risk score;

A - is the asset value;

V - is the vulnerability level;

D - is the detection confidence;

C - is the impact on confidentiality, integrity, and availability;

$$\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \lambda$$

are weight coefficients.

The response decision is defined as:

$$Response = \begin{cases} Monitor, & R < \theta_1 \\ Alert, & \theta_1 \leq R < \theta_2 \\ Block, & \theta_2 \leq R < \theta_3 \\ Isolate and Re - key, & R \geq \theta_3 \end{cases}$$

where θ_1 , θ_2 , and θ_3 are predefined decision thresholds.

Figure 1. Architecture of the quantum-resilient adaptive network security model [1], [3].

The figure describes the proposed integrated architecture. First, the user, IoT device, or edge node is verified through the Zero Trust access layer. Then,

firewall and segmentation mechanisms filter traffic and separate network zones. The IDPS and AI monitoring layer detects suspicious traffic and sends risk indicators to the risk analysis module. After that, BIKE establishes a secure session key, NTRUEncrypt encrypts data, and SPHINCS+ provides digital signature and integrity protection. Finally, the resource-aware optimization layer selects ARM or FPGA execution depending on device capability and energy requirements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed model provides protection against two major categories of threats: current network-based cyberattacks and future quantum-enabled cryptographic attacks. This is achieved by combining network security mechanisms with post-quantum cryptographic algorithms.

The first result is improved multi-layered defense. Firewalls reduce unauthorized access, segmentation limits lateral movement, IDPS detects suspicious behavior, and Zero Trust prevents automatic trust inside the network. This combination is more effective than using a single security mechanism because each layer compensates for the limitations of the others.

The second result is quantum-resistant data protection. BIKE provides secure key exchange, NTRUEncrypt ensures confidentiality, and SPHINCS+ provides message integrity and authenticity. Since these algorithms are based on different mathematical assumptions, the model reduces the risk of a single cryptographic failure.

The third result is improved resource adaptability. In resource-constrained environments, security mechanisms must be optimized for speed, memory, and energy consumption. The application-specific optimization study shows that FPGA acceleration significantly improves performance compared with ARM-based implementation.

Table 3. Performance indicators for resource-aware implementation [3]

Metric	ARM Cortex-A53	FPGA Kintex-7	Improvement
NTRUEncrypt encryption speed	180 MB/s	520 MB/s	Approximately 2.9×
SPHINCS+ signature generation	620 ops/s	1450 ops/s	Approximately 2.3×

BIKE key exchange latency	1.2 ms	0.4 ms	Approximately 3× faster
Energy consumption	3.5 mJ/op	1.1 mJ/op	About 65% lower

The fourth result is adaptive incident handling. The risk score allows the system to select a suitable response. Low-risk events are monitored, medium-risk events generate alerts, high-risk events are blocked, and critical events trigger isolation and re-keying. This approach reduces unnecessary responses while improving reaction speed during serious attacks.

Table 4. Adaptive operation modes of the proposed model

Mode	Environment	Security configuration
Full protection mode	Critical infrastructure, finance, healthcare	Zero Trust + Firewall + IDPS + BIKE + NTRUEncrypt + SPHINCS+
Energy-saving mode	Battery-powered IoT devices	Reduced signature frequency and optimized key exchange
High-throughput mode	FPGA-based edge gateway	Accelerated post-quantum encryption, signing, and key exchange
Monitoring mode	Low-risk internal communication	Firewall + IDPS + selective encryption
Incident response mode	Detected attack or anomaly	Block, isolate, re-key, and notify administrator

Resistance to common IoT attacks

In addition to quantum-related threats, the proposed model can improve resistance against common IoT attacks such as Distributed Denial-of-Service and Man-in-the-Middle attacks. In DDoS scenarios, the IDPS layer monitors abnormal traffic volume, detects unusual packet flow patterns, and forwards high-risk events to the response module for blocking or isolation. In MitM scenarios, BIKE-based secure key exchange, NTRUEncrypt-based encryption, and SPHINCS+-based digital signatures help protect the confidentiality, authenticity, and integrity of transmitted data.

Therefore, the model provides protection not only against future quantum attacks but also against current

network-level attacks frequently observed in IoT and edge computing environments. If an IoT device is compromised, segmentation limits the attacker’s movement. If data traffic is intercepted, NTRUEncrypt protects confidentiality. If a message is modified, SPHINCS+ verification detects the change. If a suspicious session is detected, the system can isolate the device and perform re-keying.

However, several challenges remain. Post-quantum cryptographic algorithms may require larger keys and signatures than classical algorithms. Integration of firewall, IDPS, Zero Trust, and PQC mechanisms increases architectural complexity. IoT devices may not always support heavy cryptographic processing. Therefore, lightweight implementation, hardware acceleration, and adaptive parameter selection are necessary.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This article proposed a quantum-resilient adaptive network security model for IoT and edge computing infrastructures. The model was developed by combining three research directions: post-quantum cryptographic algorithms for secure data transmission, advanced network security strategies for cyber resilience, and application-specific optimization of hybrid post-quantum cryptographic frameworks in resource-constrained environments.

The study showed that modern cybersecurity must address both current network attacks and future quantum threats. Firewalls, IDPS, segmentation, Zero Trust, and AI-based monitoring provide protection against conventional cyber threats. BIKE, NTRUEncrypt, and SPHINCS+ provide quantum-resistant key exchange, encryption, and digital signatures.

The proposed mathematical model makes it possible to evaluate secure transmission time, adaptive security efficiency, and event risk level. This helps select appropriate security configurations for IoT devices, edge nodes, and high-performance infrastructures.

It is recommended that organizations gradually adopt quantum-resilient adaptive security architectures. First, they should identify critical assets and vulnerable network segments. Second, they should deploy firewall,

IDPS, and Zero Trust mechanisms. Third, they should integrate post-quantum cryptography for sensitive communication. Fourth, they should use FPGA or edge acceleration where high throughput and low energy consumption are required. Fifth, they should implement automated response mechanisms such as blocking, isolation, and re-keying.

The proposed architecture should also be experimentally validated against practical IoT attack scenarios, including DDoS, MitM, spoofing, and botnet-based traffic, using real or simulated IoT testbeds. Future research should focus on testing the proposed model in real IoT and 5G networks, developing lightweight post-quantum protocols, improving AI-based anomaly detection, optimizing SPHINCS+ signature processing, and integrating the model with Security Operations Center platforms.

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